

**DESIGN AND SYNTHESIS OF SOME NOVEL 2-AZETEDINONE DERIVATIVES AS
POTENTIAL ANTI-PROLIFERTIVE AGENTS**

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Abstract:

A new series of new anti-proliferative agents 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide derivatives (6a-o) were designed based on the structure and synthesized characterized by spectral data and evaluated for anti-cancer properties against breast cancer, MCF-7, HeLa and MDA-MB-231. These β -lactam derivatives depicted significant cytotoxicity in cancer cell lines but not in normal human mammary epithelial cells, MEpiC. Interestingly, derivatives of 4-(3,4 Di bromo)-phenyl-2-oxo-azetidin rendered the compound 6f relatively most potent anti-proliferative activity with IC_{50} values of 1.02 ± 0.03 and 1.26 ± 0.03 μ M, 6.86 ± 0.009 μ M and 1.36 ± 0.03 against MCF-7, HeLa, MDA-MB-231 cancer cell lines, when compared to standard drug cisplatin with IC_{50} values of 0.91 ± 0.03 , 0.84 ± 0.02 and 0.67 ± 0.02 against MCF-7, HeLa, MDA-MB-231 cancer cell lines. Compound 6l, 6m, 6n showed less potent anti-proliferative activity when compared to aromatic aldehydes (6b, 6c, 6d, 6e) substituted on phenyl-2-oxo-azetidine against MCF-7, HeLa, MDA-MB-231 cancer cell lines. Further, Docking studies of all the molecules disclosed close hydrogen bond interactions within the binding site.

Keywords: 2-Azetidinones; anti-proliferative effect; apoptosis; Molecular docking.

1.0. INTRODUCTION:

Uncontrolled tumor growth is the cause of cancer, a serious global health issue that frequently results in high morbidity and mortality. Out of the more than 200 distinct tissue-specific malignancies, breast cancer is the most prevalent malignant illness and the second-greatest mortality of people in the world (Jemal A et al., 2008). Despite an eventual progress in cancer research, the efficacy of current drugs is minimal due to high toxicity towards normal cells and non-specificity of targets. Therapies targeting the 2-azetidinone ring system is also known as the β -lactam ring system. it is a four-membered cyclic common ring, which was first developed by Staudinger in 1907 via [2+2] cycloaddition reaction of katane and imine and this reaction is termed as the “Staudinger synthesis”. The importance of the β - lactams has been established after the discovery of the penicillin by “Alexander Flemming” in 1928 observed bacteriolysis in a nutrient broth at St. Mary’s Hospital in London. The 2-azetidinone (β -lactams) ring is a common structural feature of a number of broad spectrum β -lactams antibiotics including penicillins, cephalosporins, carbapenems, nocardicin and monobactams, which have been widely used as chemotherapeutic agents to treat bacterial infection and microbial diseases. Apart from antibiotic activity β -lactams also possess cholesterol inhibition , antithrombotic, antiviral and antitumor activities (Toraskar M et al., 2010).

It has been reported that introduction of different substituents to four membered β -lactam nucleus tend to exert profound influence in conferring promising biological activities. A large number of 3-chloro monocyclic β -lactam possesses powerful antibacterial, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anticonvulsant & antitubercular activities. They also function as enzyme inhibitors & are effective on the central nervous system (Chavan Ameya A et al., 2007). Subsequently 2- azetidinones were highlighted as a potent mechanism based inhibitor of several enzymes like human tryptase,

chymase, thrombin, leukocyte elastase, human cytomegalovirus protease and serine protease enzyme. These derivatives are also known to possess antitubercular, anti-inflammatory, antitumor, anti-HIV, antiparkinsonism, antidiabetic and vasopressin antagonist activity. (Mehta PD et al., 2010). Current clinical studies on bacterial infections and the discovery of β -lactam chemistry have resulted in significant advancement. Bacteria have continued to develop resistance against the available marketing drugs. The rising challenge of multi-drug resistance TB focuses on creating novel antibiotics that not only combat drug resistant TB but also reduce the time cycle of treatment. Meanwhile, the molecular docking technology helps to anticipate the linkage between the atom (ligand) and the target and its binding position. This gives the concept of creating an effective therapeutic candidate against the target protein (Vashi BS et., 1995).

2-Azetidinone shown a broad spectrum of activity against many infections, and significant research has been done on the synthesis of new powerful antibacterial and antifungal. 2-azetidiones (Lynch JE et al 1989 and Hegedus LS et al 1991). The antibiotic activity of azetidinone ring-containing compounds, their effectiveness in cholesterol absorption and enzyme inhibitions and their applications as synthons for various biologically important compounds make them appealing targets for medicinal synthetic chemists. 2-azetidinone scaffold possesses a wide range of promising biological activities. These compounds can be used in the treatment of variety of disease and disorders like, Thrombin inhibitory activity, (Mehata et al., PD 2010 and Fenton JW et al., 1988), antihyperlipidemic (Burnett DA et al 1998., 2022) , anti-inflammatory, (Zakaria ZA et al., 2018), anti-diabetic activity (Gervois P et al., 2007) anticancer activity,[19] vasopressin v1a antagonist (Guillon CD et al., 2007) .

Design:

Yaseen et al., 2017 reported N-(3-chloro-2-(3-nitrophenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-2-(2-((2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino)phenyl)-acetamide (**I**) showed potent anti-bacterial activity with average of effects spots equal to 18.64 mm against E. coli and average of effects spots equal to 14.77 mm against Staphylococcus saprophyticus. **Shah et al., 1992** 4-[(4-carboxyphenyl)-oxy]-3,3-diethyl-1-[(4-methyl phenylmethyl)-aminocarbonyl]-2-azetidinone (**II**) first orally active inhibitor of human leukocyte elastase (HLE). Analogs of this compound with different substituents on the urea N were synthesized and evaluated for their activity in vitro against HLE as well as *in-vivo* in a hamster lung hemorrhage model. Compounds with a methyl or a methoxy group in the para position of the benzene ring were very potent in both assays. **Gupta and Halve et al. 2015** reported 4-(3-chloro-2-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-benzenesulfonamide (**III**) was screened against several fungus. The synthesized compound (**III**) show potent antifungal activity against Aspergillus niger & Aspergillus flavus basically sulpha drugs broad spectrum antibiotics it is inhibit the dihydropterate synthatase enzyme it is essential for the synthesis of folic acid.hence we need to select the sulpha nucleus. **Heek et al.** have worked on [1-(4-fluorophenyl)-(3R)-(4-fluorophenyl)-(3S)-hydroxypropyl]-(4S) (4-hydroxyphenyl)-2-azetidinone (**IV**). They observe that ezetimibe potently and selectively inhibits the intestinal absorption of cholesterol, thereby reducing plasma cholesterol in pre-clinical models of hypercholesterolemia.

In the present study, we used molecular hybridization to design 4-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-phenylazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-4-yl)benzenesulfonamide (**6a-r**) as depicted in **Figure-2** and report the synthesis and evaluation of new anti-bacterial anti-cancer agents.

Figure 2. Design of New 2-azetidinone and sulfonamides derivatives

Materials and Methods:

2.1 Chemistry:

All chemicals including standard drugs and solvents were procured from Sigma-Aldrich, HiMedia, Bangalore, India and others and were used without further purification with the exception of liquid aldehydes which were purified by using standard procedures prior to use. Melting point for all the compounds were recorded in open capillary tubes using VEEGO VMP-D Digital melting point apparatus. FTIR spectra were done on JASCO FTIR 4100 series by using KBr pellets and are reported in cm^{-1} . Signals of ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were measured on a BRUKER-II 400 (400 MHz NMR, ^{13}C NMR 100 MHz) spectrophotometer by taking TMS as internal standard. Pre-coated TLC plates were used to check the purity of the compounds and spots were visualized by using iodine vapors and ultra-violet rays. Elemental analyses were carried out by a CHN-VarioElico Micro elemental analyzer. The estimation of biochemical parameters was carried out using commercially available test kits (Sigma-Aldrich).

2.2. Synthetic Procedure:

2.2.1. Synthetic Procedure of 4-amino-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide (3):

To a solution of 4-aminobenzene-1-sulfonyl chloride (1.0 mmol) and 5-methylfuran-3-amine (2a-c, 1.0 mmol) were dissolved together at room temperature with stirring, in 10 mL dried ethanol and reflux for 18h. The progress of the reaction monitored by TLC, after completion of the reaction The mixture was filtered to collect the solid product. The filter was washed twice with dichloromethane to dissolve the reaction product. The solvent was removed and compound 4-amino-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide (3) was collected, and purified by using column chromatography. The combined organic extracts were evaporated to give colorless to yellow solids.

2.2.2. Synthetic procedure of 4-((substituted-benzylidene)amino)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide derivatives (5a-o):

4-amino-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide (3, 10 mmol) and Substituted aromatic aldehydes (4a-o, 20 mmol) were dissolved in ethanol and allowed to stirred at room temperature for overnight. On completion of the reaction mixture was diluted with cold water (15 mL) and extracted with pet. ether (3 x 25 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was purified by column chromatography (hexanes :Ethyl acetate, (9:1)) to afford pure 4-((substituted-benzylidene)amino)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide derivatives (**5a-o**) in 80-90% yield.

2.2.3. Synthetic procedure of 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide derivatives (6a-o):

To a well stirred solution of various 4-((substituted-benzylidene) amino)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide derivatives (5a-o) (1mmol) in toluene at ambient temperature allowed stirring for 10 min. After this triethylamine was added slowly at 0°C, followed by chloro-acetyl chloride in toluene and allowed to stir with increasing temperature to 40°C until completion of reaction (6-8 h). Reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography. After completion of the reaction, cool it to room temperature, diluted with ethyl acetate, washed with brine solution, and dried over Na₂SO₄ and purified by column chromatography to get the 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide derivatives (6a-o).

Scheme-1: 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetid-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide derivatives (6a-o).

Table1: Physical data of 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide derivatives (6a-o).**General structure-I (6a-o)**

Com.	Ar	M. Form	M.Wt	M.P	Rf*	% Yield
6a	Phenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₄ S	417	150-152	0.5	49
6b	4- Chloro Phenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₄ S	451	139-141	0.8	68
6c	4-Bromo Phenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ BrClN ₃ O ₄ S	496	162-164	0.7	50
6d	4-Flouro Phenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClFN ₃ O ₄ S	435	170-172	0.8	55
6e	3,4 Di chloro	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ Cl ₃ N ₃ O ₄ S	484	190-192	0.6	70
6f	3,4 Di bromo	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ Br ₂ ClN ₃ O ₄ S;	572	198-200	0.3	52
6g	3,4 Di hydroxy	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₆ S	449	148-150	0.4	50
6h	3- Nitro	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₆ S	462	136-138	0.7	78
6i	4-Chloro-3-nitro	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₆ S	496	163-165	0.9	71
6j	3,4,5Trimethoxy phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ ClN ₃ O ₇ S	507	172-174	0.5	48
6k	4-hydroxy-3-methoxy- phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₆ S	463	210-212	0.5	45
6l	3,5- dimethyl-pyrole-2-carboxaldehyde	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	434	188-190	0.8	50
6m	3-hydroxy pyridine-2- carboxaldehyde	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₅ S	434	218-220	0.6	65
6n	4-chloro-pyrazole-3- carboxaldehyde	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₅ O ₄ S	442	159-161	0.8	78
6o	4-Bromo-1-methyl-pyrazole-3-carboxaldehyde	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ BrClN ₅ O ₄ S	500	168-170	0.5	35

*Mobile phase: hexane: ethyl acetate

2.3.0. Characterization of New 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide derivatives (6a-o):

2.3.1. 4-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-phenylazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)-benzene sulfonamide

(6a): IR spectrum (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3432.90 NH (str), 3050.71 C-H Aromatic (str), 1635.18 C=O (str), 1320.35 C=C Aromatic (str); ^1H NMR (400MHz CDCl_3 , δ ppm): 11.285 (s, 1H, NH, Amide), 7.96-7.98 (d, $J=8.0\text{Hz}$, 2H, Aromatic C-H) 7.89-7.90(d, $J=8.0$ Hz 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.75-7.78 (t, $J=16.0\text{Hz}$, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 7.43-7.47 (m, 4H, Aromatic C-H), 5.370 (s, 3H, methyl) 2.825(s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): 170.10, 165.31, 148.24, 143.40, 136.39, 135.12, 132.18, 130.40, 129.06, 128.28, 126.29, 124.32, 118.24, 60.40, 58.26.

ESI MS m/z : 419 $[\text{M}+2]^+$: Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_4\text{S}$; CHN: C, 54.61; H, 3.86; N, 10.06; S, 7.67 Found: C, 54.65; H, 3.80; N, 10.09; S, 7.60.

2.3.2. 4-(3-chloro-2-(3-chlorophenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene

sulfonamide (6b): IR spectrum (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3340.10 NH (str), 3065.20 C-H Aromatic (str), 1648.12 C=O (str), 1630.18 C=N (str), 1538.19 C=C Aromatic (str), 1360.12 C-N (str); ^1H NMR (400MHz CDCl_3 , δ ppm): 11.284 (s, 1H, NH, Amide), 7.95-7.97 (d, $J=8.0\text{Hz}$, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.85-7.87 (d, $J=8.0$ Hz 3H, Aromatic C-H), 7.73-7.76 (t, $J=16.0\text{Hz}$, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 7.40-7.44 (m, 3H, Aromatic C-H), 5.370 (s, 3H, methyl) 2.825(s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): 165.10, 160.30, 156.20, 153.10, 148.31, 145.30, 142.10, 138.41, 129.06, 128.28, 126.29, 124.31, 119.24, 50.10, 48.20. ESI MS m/z : 455 $[\text{M}+4]^+$, 453 $[\text{M}+2]^+$, 451 $[\text{M}]^+$: Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{S}$; CHN: C, 50.45; H, 3.34; N, 9.29; S, 7.09. Found: 50.48; H, 3.30; N, 9.24; S, 7.01.

2.3.3. *4-(2-(3-bromophenyl)-3-chloro-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide (6c)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3418.18 (NH (str), 3061.19 C-H Aromatic (str), 1634.18 C=O (str), 1618.11 C=N (str), 1560.20 C=C Aromatic (str), 1320.14 C-N (str): ¹H NMR (400MHz CDCl₃, δ ppm): 11.284 (s, 1H, NH, Amide), 7.93-7.95 (d, *J*=8.0Hz, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 7.88-7.90 (d, *J*=8.0 Hz 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.75-7.78 (t, *J*=16.0Hz, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 7.60-7.62 (d, *J*=8.0 Hz 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.38-7.44(m, 3H, Aromatic C-H), 5.370 (s, 3H, methyl) 2.822 (s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): 169.18, 158.10, 156.24, 154.09, 150.30, 148.20, 146.10, 135.41, 129.06, 128.28, 126.29, 124.31, 119.24, 50.23, 45.40. ESI MS m/z: 500 [M+4]⁺, 498 [M+2]⁺, 496 [M]⁺: Calc. for C₁₉H₁₅BrClN₃O₄S; CHN: C, 45.94; H, 3.04; N, 8.46; O, 12.88; S, 6.45. Found: 50.48; H, 3.12; N, 8.16; S, 6.40.

2.3.4. *4-(3-chloro-2-(3-fluorophenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide (6d)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3341.12 NH (str), 3026.92 C-H Aromatic (str), 1636.01 C=O (str), 1615.36 C=N (str), 1591.98 C=C Aromatic (str), 1382.81 C-N (str), 850.21 C-F (str). ¹H NMR (400MHz CDCl₃, δ ppm): 11.281 (s, 1H, NH, Amide), 7.84-7.86 (d, *J*=8.0Hz, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.78-7.80 (d, *J*=8.0 Hz 3H, Aromatic C-H), 7.68-7.71 (t, *J*=16.0Hz, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 7.50-7.54 (m, 3H, Aromatic C-H), 5.371 (s, 3H, methyl) 2.821(s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): 162.25, 145.19, 140.43, 131.29, 128.38, 126.02, 124.27, 121.35, 121.46, 58.31, 52.09, 48.20. ESI MS m/z: 439 [M+4]⁺, 437 [M+2]⁺, 435 [M]⁺: Calc. for C₁₉H₁₅ClFN₃O₄S; CHN: C, 52.36; H, 3.47; N, 9.64; S, 7.36. Found: C, 52.30; H, 3.40; N, 9.62; S, 7.35.

2.3.5. *4-(3-chloro-2-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide (6e)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3425.72 NH (str), 3081.17 C-H Aromatic (str), 2924.43 Aliphatic CH, 1638.12 C=O (str), 1572.70 C=C Aromatic (str), 1353.51 C=N (str),

680.25 C-Cl (Str); ¹H NMR (400MHz CDCl₃, δ ppm): 11.285 (s, 1H, NH, Amide), 7.906-7.927 (d, *J*=8.0Hz, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.703-7.724 (d, *J*=8.0 Hz 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.567-7.606 (t, *J*=16.0Hz, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 7.370-7.408 (m, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 5.370(s, 3H, methyl) 2.825(s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): 153.78, 152.34, 143.63, 142.44, 139.59, 121.08, 120.65, 120.07, 118.12, 115.65, 66.22, 54.18. ESI MS *m/z*: 490[M+6]⁺, 488 [M+4]⁺, 486[M+2]⁺, 484 [M]⁺: Calc. for C₁₉H₁₄Cl₃N₃O₄S; CHN: C, 50.45; H, 3.34; N, 9.29; S, 7.09. Found: 50.48; H, 3.30; N, 9.24; S, 7.01.

2.3.6: *4-(3-chloro-2-(3,4-dibromophenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide (6f)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3441.03 NH (str), 3061.10 C-H Aromatic (str), 1648.68 C=O (str), 1628.10 C=N (str), 1531.07 C=C Aromatic (str), 680.25 C-Cl (Str); ¹H NMR (400MHz CDCl₃, δ ppm): 11.282 (s, 1H, NH, Amide), 7.90-7.92 (d, *J*=8.0Hz, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.82-7.84 (d, *J*=8.0 Hz 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.76-7.79 (t, *J*=16.0Hz, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 7.62(s, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 5.371(s, 3H, methyl) 2.820 (s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): 160.12, 158.40, 148.30, 140.24, 124.19, 121.08, 120.65, 120.07, 118.12, 115.65, 66.22, 54.18. ESI MS *m/z*: 581 [M+6]⁺, 579 [M+4]⁺, 577 [M+2]⁺, 575 [M]⁺: Calc. for C₁₉H₁₄Br₂ClN₃O₄S; CHN: C, 39.64; H, 2.45; Br, 27.76; N, 7.30; S, 5.57. Found: C, 39.64; H, 2.45; Br, 27.76; N, 7.30; S, 5.57.

2.3.7. *4-(3-chloro-2-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide (6g)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3410.09 NH (str), 3048.15 C-H Aromatic (str), 2980.70 C-H Aliphatic (str), 1632.07 C=O (str), 1528.05 C=C Aromatic (str), 1378.23 C-N (str): ¹H NMR (400MHz CDCl₃, δ ppm): 11.282 (s, 1H, amide NH), 7.906-7.927 (d, *J*=8.4Hz, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.703-7.724 (d, *J*=8.0, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.567-7.606 (m, 3H, Aromatic C-H), 7.370-7.408 (d, *J*=8.2, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 5.371(s, 3H, methyl), 4.689 (s, 3H, OH), 3.841

(s, 3H, OH), 2.820 (s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): 161.32, 159.10, 150.10, 145.24, 134.17, 131.08, 130.10, 126.65, 124.07, 121.01, 120.01, 118.12, 115.65, 68.20, 54.18. ESI MS m/z: 451 $[\text{M}+2]^+$, 449 $[\text{M}]^+$: Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_6\text{S}$; CHN: C, 50.73; H, 3.58; N, 9.34; S, 7.13. Found: C, 50.78; H, 3.54; N, 9.38; S, 7.10

2.3.8. *4-(3-chloro-2-(3-nitrophenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide (6h)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3406.12 NH (str), 3061.20 C-H Aromatic (str), 2960.52 C-H Aliphatic (str), 1630.61 C=O (str), 1618.367 C=N (str), 1545.67 C=C Aromatic (str): ^1H NMR (400MHz CDCl_3 , δ ppm): 11.284 (s, 1H, NH, Amide), 7.94-7.97 (d, $J=8.0\text{Hz}$, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.89-7.90(d, $J=8.0\text{ Hz}$ 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.72-7.75 (t, $J=16.0\text{Hz}$, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 7.40-7.45 (m, 5H, Aromatic C-H), 5.370 (s, 3H, methyl) 2.825(s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): 160.11, 158.72, 152.24, 143.40, 136.39, 135.12, 132.18, 121.88, 120.65, 120.07, 119.52, 115.35, 61.52, 47.12. ESI MS m/z: 464 $[\text{M}+2]^+$: Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_6\text{S}$; CHN: C, 49.30; H, 3.27; N, 12.10; S, 6.93 Found: C, 49.25; H, 3.24; N, 12.15; S, 6.90.

2.3.9. *4-(3-chloro-2-(4-chloro-3-nitrophenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide (6i)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3476.12 NH (str), 3065.20 C-H Aromatic (str), 2950.52 C-H Aliphatic (str), 1635.65 C=O (str), 1620.367 C=N (str), 1535.67 C=C Aromatic (str), 680.25 C-Cl (Str); ^1H NMR (400MHz CDCl_3 , δ ppm): 11.284 (s, 1H, NH, Amide), 7.908-7.915 (d, $J=8.0\text{ Hz}$, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.803-7.824 (d, $J=8.0\text{ Hz}$ 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.567-7.606 (t, $J=16.0\text{Hz}$, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 7.401-7.408 (m, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 5.374 (s, 3H, methyl) 2.821(s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): 161.47, 150.41, 148.11, 146.43, 142.01, 138.08, 131.29, 130.25, 129.32, 128.42, 126.02, 125.61, 121.88, 121.46, 53.83, 52.95. ESI MS m/z: 500 $[\text{M}+4]^+$, 498 $[\text{M}+2]^+$, 496 $[\text{M}]^+$: Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_6\text{S}$; CHN: C,

45.89; H, 2.84; N, 11.27; S, 6.45; Found: C, 45.80; H, 2.81; N, 11.23; S, 6.41.

2.3.10 *4-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)azetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide (6j)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3332.71 NH (str), 3053.61 C-H Aromatic (str), 2968.88 C-H Aliphatic (str), 1615.87 C=O (str), 1573.67 C=C Aromatic (str), 1367.55 C-N (str), 864.12 (C-Cl): ^1H NMR (400MHz CDCl_3 , δ ppm): 11.285 (s, 1H, amide NH), 7.867-7.913 (m, 3H, Aromatic C-H), 7.462-7.563 (m, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.373-7.395 (d, $J=8.2$, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 6.378(s, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 5.351 (s, 3H, methyl), 3.797 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 3.790(s, 6H, OCH_3) 2.820 (s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): 168.65, 161.15, 142.08, 132.54, 131.08, 129.35, 129.09, 128.56, 128.14, 126.88, 125.27, 124.48, 124.48, 114.02, 60.32, 42.48 ESI MS m/z : 509 $[\text{M}+2]^+$, 507 $[\text{M}]^+$: Calc. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_7\text{S}$; CHN: C, 52.02; H, 4.37; N, 8.27; S, 6.31 Found: 52.12; H, 4.30; N, 8.20; S, 6.30.

2.3.11. *4-(3-chloro-2-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide (6k)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3456.12 NH (str), 3093.20 C-H Aromatic (str), 2949.42 C-H Aliphatic (str), 1640.52 C=O (str), 1630.17 C=N (str), 1545.87 C=C Aromatic (str), 868.12 (C-Cl): ^1H NMR (400MHz CDCl_3 , δ ppm): 11.280 (s, 1H, amide NH), 7.911-7.943 (m, 3H, Aromatic C-H), 7.762-7.813 (d, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.573-7.695 (d, $J=8.2$, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 6.378(s, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 5.351 (s, 3H, methyl), 3.798 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 3.085(s, 1H, OH) 2.825 (s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): 160.15, 159.15, 152.08, 142.14, 138.14, 130.15, 129.01, 128.16, 127.10, 126.18, 125.27, 124.48, 120.48, 119.02, 60.32, 42.48; ESI MS m/z : 465 $[\text{M}+2]^+$, 463 $[\text{M}]^+$: Calc. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_6\text{S}$; CHN: C, 51.78; H, 3.91; N, 9.06; S, 6.91; Found: C, 51.74; H, 3.90; N, 9.02; S, 6.94.

2.3.12. *4-(3-chloro-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrrol-2-yl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide (6l)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3404.10 NH (str), 3058.10 C-H Aromatic

(str), 2950.01 C-H Aliphatic (str), 1631.13 C=O (str), 1618.37 C=N (str), 1538.17 C=C Aromatic (str), 689.12 C-Cl (Str); ¹H NMR (400MHz CDCl₃, δ ppm): 11.280 (s, 1H, NH, Amide), 7.861-7.902 (d, *J*=8.0 Hz, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.667-7.906 (m, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.301-7.321 (m, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 5.368 (s, 3H, methyl), 4.891 (m, 6H, aliphatic), 2.821(s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): 160.10, 158.38, 156.15, 150.13, 148.01, 146.08, 141.29, 138.20, 130.32, 128.42, 126.02, 125.61, 121.88, 121.46, 63.80, 55.91. ESI MS m/z: 436[M+2]⁺, 434 [M]⁺: Calc. for C₁₉H₁₉ClN₄O₄S; CHN: C, 52.47; H, 4.40; N, 12.88; S, 7.37 Found: C, 52.40; H, 4.48; N, 12.80; S, 7.30

2.3.13. *4-(3-chloro-2-(3-hydroxypyridin-2-yl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide (6m)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3425.32NH (str), 3069.10 C-H Aromatic (str), 2958.10 C-H Aliphatic (str), 1638.15 C=O (str), 1530.10 C=C Aromatic (str), 1380.15 C-N (str): ¹H NMR (400MHz CDCl₃, δ ppm):11.282 (s, 1H, amide NH), 7.896-7.910 (t, *J*=16.4Hz, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.710-7.721 (d, *J*=8.0, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.567-7.606 (m, 3H, Aromatic C-H), 7.461-7.468 (d, *J*=8.2, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 5.371(s, 3H, methyl), 4.689 (s, 3H, OH), 3.841 (s, 3H, OH), 2.820 (s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): 160.30, 158.20, 156.18, 150.14, 144.10, 141.08, 138.15, 136.60, 130.07, 128.01, 120.01, 119.10, 114.65, 50.20, 44.18. ESI MS m/z: 436 [M+2]⁺, 434 [M]⁺: Calc. for C₁₈H₁₅ClN₄O₅S; CHN: C, 49.72; H, 3.48; Cl, 8.15; N, 12.88; O, 18.40; S, 7.37. Found: C, 49.70; H, 3.45; N, 12.81; S, 7.31.

2.3.14. *4-(3-chloro-2-(4-chloro-1H-pyrazol-3-yl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide (6n)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3450.10 NH (str), 3071.15 C-H Aromatic (str), 2960.12 C-H Aliphatic (str), 1640.15 C=O (str), 1618.37 C=N (str), 1530.17 C=C Aromatic (str), 685.15 C-Cl (Str); ¹H NMR (400MHz CDCl₃, δ ppm): 11.281 (s, 1H, NH, Amide), 7.914-7.925 (d, *J*=8.0 Hz, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.560-7.574 (m, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.402-7.404 (d,

1H, Aromatic C-H), 5.369 (s, 3H, methyl) 2.820(s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): 160.40, 159.40, 150.11, 149.42, 146.05, 140.03, 136.29, 130.20, 129.31, 128.42, 126.02, 125.60, 124.48, 122.16, 58.13, 50.15. ESI MS m/z: 446 [M+4]⁺, 444[M+2]⁺, 442[M]⁺ : Calc. for C₁₆H₁₃Cl₂N₅O₄S ; CHN: C, 43.45; H, 2.96; N, 15.83; S, 7.25; Found: C, C, 43.41; H, 2.90; N, 15.80; S, 7.20.

2.3.15. *4-(2-(4-bromo-1-methyl-1H-pyrazol-3-yl)-3-chloro-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide (6o)*: IR spectrum (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3348.10 NH (str), 3051.12 C-H Aromatic (str), 1634.21 C=O (str), 1628.16 C=N (str), 1560.10 C=C Aromatic (str), 1381.10 C-N (str), 684.21 C-Br (str). ¹H NMR (400MHz CDCl₃, δ ppm): 11.284 (s, 1H, NH, Amide), 7.84-7.86 (d, *J*=8.0Hz, 2H, Aromatic C-H), 7.78-7.80 (d, *J*=8.0 Hz 3H, Aromatic C-H), 7.68-7.71 (t, *J*=16.0Hz, 1H, Aromatic C-H), 7.50-7.54 (m, 3H, Aromatic C-H), 5.371 (s, 3H, methyl) 2.821(s, 2H, Azetidin-2-one). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): 160.25, 148.10, 145.13, 138.19, 130.31, 128.02, 125.27, 124.35, 120.41, 60.11, 56.09, 50.21. ESI MS m/z: 502 [M+2]⁺, 500 [M]⁺ : Calc. for C₁₇H₁₅BrClN₅O₄S; CHN: C, 40.77; H, 3.02; N, 13.99; S, 6.40; Found: C, 40.70; H, 3.05; N, 13.94; S, 6.45.

3.0 Molecular docking studies:

Molecular docking studies of **New 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide derivatives (6a-o)** were carried out using Schrödinger software (Schrödinger, Version 2023-4) installed on Intel Xenon W 3565 processor and Ubuntu enterprise (version 14.04) as an operating system. The ligands were drawn by using ChemDraw 18.0. With the help of XP Visualizers (Schrödinger, Version 2023-4). The results were analyzed.

Schrodinger software (Version 2023-4; Schrodinger) (Glide module). The ligands used as inputs for docking were sketched by using ChemDraw software. Ligands were prepared by using OPLS3e force field in Ligprep (Dizdaroglu et al. 2020) (Version 2023-3, Schrodinger) was used to carry out, the docking studies This minimization helps to assign bond orders, Addition of the hydrogens to the ligands. The generated output file containing the best conformations of the ligands was used for docking studies. Protein was prepared by using the protein preparation wizard (Dizdaroglu et al. 2020) (Version 2023-3, Schrodinger). Charges were assigned to the protein after addition of hydrogen atoms Generated Het states using epik at pH 7.2. The protein was pre-processed refined, modified by analyzing workspace. Atoms which are non-significant were excluded from the crystal structure. Finally, the protein was optimized by using OPLS3e force field. A receptor grid was generated around the cocrystal ligand (X-ray pose of the ligand in the protein). Ligand centroid was selected to generate grid box, and Vander Waal radius of receptor atoms was scaled to 1.00 Å having a partial atomic charge of 0.25. From the output, The best-docked structure was determined using Glide docking score. Poses of the generated output of ligands after docking was analyzed by the help of XP Visualizer (Version 2023-3, Schrodinger). The results are presented in **Tables-2** and **Figures-1** and **2**.

Table 2: Binding Energies (Kcal/mol), No. of HBs and Binding Sites

S.No	Compound	Docking score of MCF-7 (6ENV)	Docking score of HELA (7ACF)	Docking score of MDA-MB-231 (6VJ3)
1	6a	-5.971	-4.782	-5.102
2	6b	-4.707	-3.723	-4.124
3	6c	-10.057	-9.415	-9.015
4	6d	-4.146	-3.714	-4.254
5	6e	-6.861	-7.395	-6.125
6	6f	11.401	-10.711	-9.711
7	6g	-5.381	-3.484	-4.214
8	6h	-4.712	-3.489	-4.105
9	6i	-3.942	-3.526	-3.142
10	6j	-4.386	-3.475	-3.434
11	6k	-5.386	-3.241	-3.547
12	6l	-6.934	-5.224	-5.021
13	6m	-5.270	-4.252	-4.252
14	6n	-4.352	-5.149	-4.341
15	6o	-9.352	-10.721	-9.141
16	Cocrystal Ligand	5.787	-9.068	-9.068

Figure-1: 2D of compound 6f docked into the active site MDA-MB-231 (6VJ3)

Figure-2: Binding poses and interactions of compound 6f to the binding sites of target protein HeLa receptor (7-ACF)

Figure-3: Binding poses and interactions of compound **6F** to the binding sites of target protein MCF-7 receptor (6ENV)

3.1. Results and discussions of molecular docking:

In-vitro studies of synthesized compounds New 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide derivatives (**6a-o**) showed the potential anti-proliferative activity and among the compounds **6f** showed promising anti-cancer activity. These result encouraged us to perform docking studies to get the insight in to the binding mode of synthesized compounds within binding pocket of MCF-7 (6ENV), HeLa (7-ACF) and MDA-MB-231 (6VJ3). All structures of ligands were built using maestro and further prepared using LigPrep form Schrodinger package. Protein structures were obtained from the Protein Data Bank MCF-7 (6ENV), HeLa (7-ACF) and MDA-MB-231 (6VJ3). and necessary correction to the protein structure were done using Protein Preparation Wizard in Schrodinger package. Docking studies were performed using Glide docking software and docking protocol was validated by docking the cocrystal ligand which resulted with RMSD of docked conformation and cocrystal

ligand pose was found to be 0.6. The binding interactions of compounds with MCF-7 (6ENV), HeLa (7-ACF) and MDA-MB-231 (6VJ3) have been listed in **Table- 3, Figure- 1 and Figure 2 and Figure-3**. Docking study was performed on binding poses of synthesized compounds with MCF-7 (6ENV), HeLa (7-ACF) and MDA-MB-231 (6VJ3) have shown that these molecules bind well within binding pocket of enzyme. Among the all synthesized molecules, the compound with potent anti-proliferative activity **6f**, has shown the highest binding score(**11.401, -10.711 and -9.711** against MCF-7 (6ENV), HeLa (7-ACF) and MDA-MB-231 (6VJ3). In superimposed pose of **6f**, with cocrystal ligand, azatadine ring was coinciding with skeleton of cocrystal ligand as depicted in **Figure-1**.

4.0. Anti-proliferative activity (MTT Assay method):

The anti-proliferative activity of synthetic compounds New 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide derivatives (6a-o) was evaluated by using (3-4, 5- dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2, 5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay. The MTT test works by converting tetrazolium soluble salt into formazan crystals using live cells' mitochondrial NAD and NADH-dehydrogenases. Human breast cancer cell lines MCF-7, HeLa, MDA-MB-231, and primary mammary epithelial control cells MEpiC were plated in a 96-well plate at a density of 5×10^3 cells per well. Cells were treated with the synthesized compounds (6a-o) at a range of concentrations from 0.1, 0.3, 1, 3, 10, 30, 100 μM for 48 h at 37 °C in a humidified CO₂ incubator followed by removal of the supernatant medium and addition of MTT solution (0.5 mg/mL). MTT-added cells were incubated for 4 hours at 37 °C in a humidified circumstance. The medium is then removed and allowed to dry at room temperature in the dark. The generated formazan crystals were then dissolved with DMSO, and the end product was measured using a microplate spectrophotometer. (Perkin Elmer Enspire, Germany) [47].

Cisplatin , was used as positive control for all the experiments. The cytotoxicity was expressed as the concentration of sample that inhibited 50% of cell growth (IC₅₀) (Archana S et al., 2015).

Table 3: Anti-cancer activity data of New 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide derivatives (6a-o):

S.No	Comp	Ar	MCF-7	HELA	MDA-MB-231	MEpiC
1	6a	Phenyl	6.10±0.02	7.17±0.02	6.72±0.02	NA
2	6b	4- Chloro Phenyl	2.32±0.04	2.02±0.04	3.52±0.04	85.02±0.04
3	6c	4-Bromo Phenyl	1.12±0.02*	1.78±0.04*	1.82±0.02*	NA
4	6d	4-Flouro Phenyl	2.35±0.06	6.41±0.03	2.35±0.06	NA
5	6e	3,4 Di chloro	1.80±0.02	5.35±0.03	1.80±0.02	95.35±0.03
6	6f	3,4 Di bromo	1.02±0.03**	1.26±0.03**	1.36±0.03**	NA
7	6g	3,4 Di hydroxy	2.35±0.02	2.45±0.03	2.15±0.02	NA
8	6h	3- Nitro	2.08±0.03	2.38±0.03	2.98±0.03	NA
9	6i	4-Chloro-3-nitro	3.92±0.03	3.91±0.02	3.92±0.03	NA
10	6j	3,4,5Trimethoxy phenyl	2.90±0.02	2.64±0.02	2.90±0.02	97.64±0.02
11	6k	4-hydroxy-3-methoxy- phenyl	3.02±0.04	3.59±0.02	3.02±0.04	>100
12	6l	3,5- dimethyl-pyrole-2-carboxaldehyde	4.65±0.03	4.24±0.03	4.95±0.03	>100
13	6m	3-hydroxy pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde	4.91±0.02	4.86±0.03	4.21±0.02	NA
14	6n	4-chloro-pyrazole-3- carboxaldehyde	4.58±0.03	4.15±0.04	3.98±0.03	>100
15	6o	4-Bromo-1-methyl-pyrazole-3- carboxaldehyde	1.65±0.06*	1.92±0.06*	2.05±0.06*	NA
16	-	Cisplatin	0.91±0.03	0.84±0.02	0.67±0.02	NA

Results were expressed as (mean±SD) analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by tukey's

multiple comparison test with *p<0.05, **p<0.01 as significant

4.1. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS :

4.1.1. Chemistry:

To a mixture of 4-aminobenzene-1-sulfonyl chloride (1.0 mmol; **1**) and 5-methylfuran-3-amine (**2a-c**, 1.0 mmol) were dissolved, in 10 mL dried ethanol followed by reflux for 18h. The progress of the reaction monitored by TLC, after completion of the reaction The mixture was filtered to collect the solid product 4-amino-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide (**3**). The compound (**3**, 10mmol) and Substituted aromatic aldehydes (**4a-o**, 20 mmol) were dissolved in ethanol and allowed to stirred at room temperature for overnight. On completion of the reaction mixture was diluted with cold water (15 mL) and extracted with pet. Ether. The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was afford pure 4-((substituted-benzylidene)amino)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide derivatives (**5a-o**). A mixture of methoxy acetyl chloride and -((substituted-benzylidene)amino)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide in presence of triethyl amine as base in toluene solvent system (Scheme 1). Table 1 demonstrates the New 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide derivatives (**6a-o**) that were synthesized using the aforementioned methods. By evaluating different base and solvent combinations, the reaction conditions were adapted. Triethyl amine performed effectively as a base, whereas toluene worked well as a solvent to produce the corresponding 2-azetidinone derivatives (**6a-o**) in higher yields. Using this methodology, different aldehyde compounds were treated, and **scheme 1** demonstrates that in every case, the reactions produced 2-azitidinone derivatives and were clean, simple to solve and extremely efficient. he newly synthesized 2-azetidinone derivatives were obtained in excellent yields and characterized by spectroscopic techniques like ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR, ESI-MS.

The FTIR spectra of New 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide derivatives (6a-o) derivatives showed absorption bands between 3480-3300 cm^{-1} due to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of primary amine group and aromatic CH stretching vibrations observed at 3050-3080 cm^{-1} and amidic carbonyl group showing a band at 1700-1600 cm^{-1} . The ^1H NMR spectrum of the same compounds showed a broad peak at $\delta \sim 11.280$, which indicated the presence of primary amine. Aromatic protons observed in the range of 7.0-8.0 ppm and additional methyl protons were observed in range of 5.270-5.280 ppm. and all the alkanyl protons in the range of 2.5-5.0ppm and aromatic protons in the range of 7.0-8.0 ppm. Hydroxy protons in the range of 4.678-4.710 ppm. Methoxy protons in the range of 3.790-3.780 ppm. The ESI mass spectrum of all the compounds showed peaks at relevant M+H m/z and complemented the FTIR & ^1H NMR spectra for the confirmation of expected structures of all the compounds. The Physical data of the final compounds has been listed in **Table 1**.

4.1.2. *In vitro* anti-cancer activity:

The MTT cell viability assay was used for evaluating the anti-proliferative activity of synthesized New 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide derivatives (6a-o) in human breast cancer cell lines MCF-7, HeLa and MDA-MB-231, as well as non-transformed normal human mammary epithelial cells (MEpiC). The anti-proliferative activity profile of these compounds showed a better specificity towards both the breast adenocarcinoma cell line MCF-7, HeLa and the breast cancer cell line MDA-MB-231 when compared to the control cells MEpiC. Among all the 15 compounds evaluated, only compounds 6c, 6f and 6n were observed to be effective against both the cell types with IC_{50} values $\leq 10 \mu\text{M}$. 4-(3,4 Di bromo)-phenyl-2-oxo-azetidin rendered the compound 6f relatively more

active against MCF-7, HeLa, MDA-MB-231 cancer cell lines than 3,4 Dichloro (6e) atoms at the same position of phenyl 2-oxo-azetidine derivatives. The compound 6f was observed to be the most potent anti-proliferative activity with IC_{50} values of 1.02 ± 0.03 and 1.26 ± 0.03 μM , 6.86 ± 0.009 μM and 1.36 ± 0.03 against MCF-7, HeLa, MDA-MB-231 cancer cell lines. Unsubstituted phenyl 2-oxo-azetidine derivative that is *4-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-phenylazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)-benzene sulfonamide (6a)*, were ineffective in decreasing the proliferative activity with IC_{50} values of 6.10 ± 0.02 , 7.17 ± 0.02 and 6.72 ± 0.02 against MCF-7, HeLa, MDA-MB-231 cancer cell lines. Compound 6l, 6m, 6n showed less potent anti-proliferative activity when compared to aromatic aldehydes (6b, 6c, 6d, 6e) substituted on phenyl-2-oxo-azetidine against MCF-7, HeLa, MDA-MB-231 cancer cell lines. the presence of methyl group at the 5-position of isoxazole moiety was observed to impart a potent antiproliferative property. Cisplatin a standard anti-cancer agent was used as positive control. These compounds were either ineffective or 10-fold less potent against the human MEpiC cell line in causing cytotoxicity, thus suggesting their non-toxic property against normal cells.

5.0. Conclusions:

In conclusion, the synthesis of New 4-(3-chloro-2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoazetidin-1-yl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide derivatives (6a-o) were evaluated for their anti-proliferative activity, which depicted three potent compounds **6c**, **6f**, **6o** with similar IC_{50} ($\leq 10\mu M$) values in both breast cancer cell lines MCF-7, HeLa and MDA-MB-231, along with pro-apoptotic activity as compared to the standard drug. Among these compounds, the most potent **6f** treatment to breast cancer cells led to an increased expression of pro-apoptotic genes, Molecular docking studies revealed that possible binding mode of **6f**, potent β -lactam analogue in the MCF-7, HeLa and MDA-MB-231 receptor with at list two hydrogen bond interactions barring few compounds.

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REFERENCES:

Archana S, Geesala R, Rao NB, Satpati S, Puroshottam G, Panasa A, Dixit A, Das A, Srivastava AK. Development of constrained tamoxifen mimics and their antiproliferative properties against breast cancer cells. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*. 2015 Feb 1;25(3):680-4.

Burnett DA, Caplen MA, Browne ME, Zhau H, Altmann SW, Davis Jr HR, Clader JW. Synthesis of fluorescent biochemical tools related to the 2-azetidinone class of cholesterol absorption inhibitors. *Bioorganic & medicinal chemistry letters*. 2002 Feb 11;12(3):315-8.

Chavan AA, Pai NR. Synthesis and biological activity of N-substituted-3-chloro-2-azetidinones. *Molecules*. 2007 Nov 12;12(11):2467-77.

Fenton JW. Regulation of thrombin generation and functions. In *Seminars in thrombosis and hemostasis* 1988 Jul (Vol. 14, No. 03, pp. 234-240).

Gervois P, Fruchart JC, Staels B. Drug Insight: mechanisms of action and therapeutic applications for agonists of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors. *Nature clinical practice Endocrinology & metabolism*. 2007 Feb;3(2):145-56.

Guillon CD, Koppel GA, Brownstein MJ, Chaney MO, Ferris CF, Lu SF, Fabio KM, Miller MJ, Heindel ND, Hunden DC, Cooper RD. Azetidinones as vasopressin V1a antagonists. *Bioorganic & medicinal chemistry*. 2007 Mar 1;15(5):2054-80.

Gupta A, Halve AK. Synthesis & antifungal screening of novel azetidin-2-ones. *Open Chemistry Journal*. 2015 Feb 27;2(1).

Halve AK, Bhadauria D, Dubey R. N/C-4 substituted azetidin-2-ones: synthesis and preliminary evaluation as new class of antimicrobial agents. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*. 2007 Jan 15;17(2):341-5.

Hegedus LS, Montgomery J, Narukawa Y, Snustad DC. A contribution to the confusion surrounding the reaction of ketenes with imines to produce beta-lactams. A comparison of stereoselectivity dependence on the method of ketene generation: acid chloride/triethylamine vs photolysis of chromium carbene complexes. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 1991 Jul;113(15):5784-91.

Jemal A, Siegel R, Ward E, Hao Y, Xu J, Murray T, Thun MJ. Cancer statistics, 2008. *CA Cancer J Clin*. 2008 Mar-Apr;58(2):71-96.

Lynch JE, Riseman SM, Laswell WL, Volante RP, Smith GB, Shinkai I, Tschaen DM. Mechanism of an acid chloride-imine reaction by low-temperature FT-IR: beta-lactam formation occurs exclusively through a ketene intermediate. *The Journal of Organic Chemistry*. 1989 Aug;54(16):3792-6.

Mehta P, Sengar N, Subrahmanyam E, Satyanarayana D. Synthesis and biological activity studies of some thiazolidinones and azetidinones. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*. 2006 Jan 1;68(1).

Mehta PD, Sengar NP, Pathak AK. 2-Azetidinone—a new profile of various pharmacological activities. *European journal of medicinal chemistry*. 2010 Dec 1;45(12):5541-60.;

Shah SK, Dorn CP Jr, Finke PE, Hale JJ, Haggmann WK, Brause KA, Chandler GO, Kissinger AL, Ashe BM, Weston H, et al. Orally active beta-lactam inhibitors of human leukocyte elastase-1. Activity of 3,3-diethyl-2-azetidinones. *J Med Chem.* 1992 Oct 16;35(21):3745-54.

Toraskar M, Kulkarni V, Kadam V. Azetidinone: A bioactive moiety. *J. Pharm. Res.* 2010 Jan; 3:169-73.

Van Heek M, France CF, Compton DS, McLeod RL, Yumibe NP, Alton KB, Sybertz EJ, Davis HR Jr. In vivo metabolism-based discovery of a potent cholesterol absorption inhibitor, SCH58235, in the rat and rhesus monkey through the identification of the active metabolites of SCH48461. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther.* 1997 Oct;283(1):157-63.

Vashi BS, Mehta DS, Shah VH. Synthesis and Biological Activity of 4 - Thiazolidinones, 2 - Azetidinones, 4 - Imidazolinone Derivatives Having Thymol Moiety. *ChemInform.* 1995 Nov 21;26(47):no-.

Yaseen YS, Farhan MS, Salih SJ. Synthesis and evaluation of new diclofenac acid having 2-azetidinone. *Der Pharma Chemica.* 2017;9:44-9.

Zakaria ZA, Abdul Ghani ZD, Raden Mohd. Nor RN, Gopalan HK, Sulaiman MR, Mat Jais AM, Somchit MN, Kader AA, Ripin J. Antinociceptive, anti-inflammatory, and antipyretic properties of an aqueous extract of *Dicranopteris linearis* leaves in experimental animal models. *Journal of natural medicines.* 2008 Apr;62:179-87.